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Hydrogen generation by Alcohol Electrolysis

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Abstract

In the ongoing global shift towards a sustainable and low-carbon energy landscape, hydrogen is increasingly recognized as a crucial energy carrier. It serves as an effective solution to tackle climate change and facilitate the decarbonization of various sectors, including energy, industry, and transportation.

Alcohol electrolysis represents an emerging technology for the sustainable production of hydrogen and chemicals. This electrochemical process involves the oxidation of alcohols, such as methanol or ethanol, in proton (PEM) or anion exchange membrane (AEM)-based cells, offering a promising alternative to water electrolysis. One of the main advantages of alcohol oxidation is the reduction of theoretical energy demand compared to water oxidation, making it a more efficient solution for hydrogen generation at the cathode side. The oxygen evolution reaction (OER) from water takes place at the anode of the electrolyzer and represents the rate-determining step in the overall water electrolysis process ($E_{rev}=1.23$ V). This reaction demands a significant energy input due to thermodynamic and kinetic factors. To overcome this limit, the oxidation of short-chain alcohols can serve as a viable substitute for the OER due to the lower reversible potentials of 0.016 and 0.084 V vs. RHE for methanol and ethanol, respectively.

In-house 50 wt.% Pt₁Ru₁ catalysts supported on high-surface-area carbon (Ketjenblack, abbreviated as KB) were synthesized by the sulphite complex route to study this process. Two different procedures involving either a direct mixing of Pt-sulphite and Ru-sulphite complexes or Pt-sulphite preparation and subsequent impregnation of Ru precursor were adopted for the bimetallic species. Scanning Transmission Electron Microscopy-Energy Dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (S/TEM-EDX), X-ray diffraction (XRD), and X-ray fluorescence (XRF) spectroscopy were used to analyze the catalysts' structures, compositions, and morphologies. Lastly, the activity, performance, and durability of alcohol electrooxidation were evaluated using rotating disc electrodes (RDE) and alcohol electrolysis cells in acidic and alkaline conditions.

Introduction

To combat climate change and achieve sustainable development, it is essential to transition away from fossil-based energy sources. Solar panels and wind turbines represent the primary large-scale renewable energy technologies [1-3]. However, due to the intermittent and unpredictable nature of solar and wind power, driven by weather variability, there is increasing focus on sustainable energy storage solutions, particularly using hydrogen (H₂) as a clean energy carrier [4,5].

Hydrogen can be stored and later used in polymer electrolyte fuel cells (PEFCs), where it is oxidized at the anode while oxygen is reduced at the cathode, separated by a membrane. This electrochemical process generates electricity and water as the only byproduct [6,7].

Among current hydrogen production methods, water electrolysis (WE) is considered the most environmentally friendly, especially when powered by renewable energy sources, since it emits no direct carbon emissions [8]. In WE, the hydrogen evolution reaction (HER) occurs at the cathode and the oxygen evolution reaction (OER) at the anode. However, the OER is the main bottleneck due to its high thermodynamic and kinetic barriers, requiring substantial energy input [9].

To address this, the electrooxidation of small organic molecules, such as short-chain alcohols, offers a promising alternative to the OER. For example, methanol and ethanol have much lower reversible oxidation potentials (0.016 V and 0.084 V vs. RHE, respectively) compared to water's OER (1.23 V vs. RHE), or thermoneutral potentials of 0.227 V and 0.301 V versus 1.48 V for OER [10]. While alcohol oxidation is traditionally explored in the context of direct alcohol fuel cells (DAFCs) due to their high energy density and liquid fuel advantages [11–12], its application in electroreforming (ER), where alcohols are oxidized at the anode to generate hydrogen at the cathode, is gaining traction. ER systems, though requiring external energy input ($\Delta G > 0$), are potentially more energy-efficient than standard polymer electrolyte membrane (PEM) water electrolysis. When alcohols derived from biomass are used, the ER process becomes even more attractive for industrial applications, offering cost savings and improved sustainability, especially with the aid of efficient electrocatalysts [13].

Complete oxidation of these organic compounds, ideally to CO₂, results in higher system efficiency. Alternatively, partial oxidation can yield valuable chemical intermediates, depending on the desired outcome.

In systems utilizing a proton exchange membrane, protons generated at the anode migrate across the membrane and can be reduced at the cathode to form hydrogen gas, as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Sketch of the hydrogen production by methanol electrolysis in an electroreforming cell

1. Scientific Approach

A 50% Pt₁Ru₁/C anode catalyst was synthesized using a simple method involving a platinum sulphite complex, followed by impregnation onto a high-surface-area carbon support (Ketjenblack, referred to as KB) and the addition of a ruthenium precursor. The methanol electrooxidation behavior of the catalyst was investigated under acidic conditions using a rotating disk electrode setup, as well as in an electroreformer (ER) cell equipped with a PtRu/C//Nafion115 proton exchange membrane (PEM)//Pt/C MEA, to assess its activity, performance, and short-term durability.

2. Experiments

Electrochemical tests of the catalysts were conducted at room temperature using a standard three-electrode setup with a rotating disk electrode (RDE) configuration. A Hg/Hg₂SO₄ electrode saturated with K₂SO₄ was employed as the reference electrode, while a high-surface-area platinum wire served as the counter electrode. The working electrode consisted of a 5 mm glassy carbon (GC) disk onto which the catalyst thin film was deposited. To achieve a platinum loading of 50 μg·cm⁻², the 50% Pt₁Ru₁/KB catalysts were sonicated for 30 minutes in a water:isopropyl alcohol mixture (3:1 v/v) containing 30% Nafion ionomer. The resulting catalyst ink was then drop-cast onto the GC disk. Before each measurement, the GC surface was polished using an OP-Felt cloth and an alumina suspension.

The base electrolyte used was 0.5 M H₂SO₄. To evaluate the catalytic activity towards methanol oxidation reaction, methanol was added to the base electrolyte to reach a concentration of 2 M. The methanol oxidation reaction (MOR) activity was measured by linear sweep voltammetry (LSV) at a scan rate of 5 mV·s⁻¹ over the potential range of 0–0.75 V vs. RHE. All electrochemical measurements were carried out using a Metrohm Autolab potentiostat/galvanostat.

Commercial gas diffusion layer (GDL)-coated carbon paper, specifically Sigracet 39BB, was employed as the backing layer for both the anode and cathode in the electrodes prepared for the electroreforming experiments in a complete full cell. The 50% Pt₁Ru₁/KB catalyst was dispersed in a 3:1 (v/v) water:isopropyl alcohol mixture, combined with 33 wt.% Nafion® ionomer (Ion Power, München, Germany; 5% solution), and sonicated thoroughly. This catalytic ink was then applied to the GDL using an airbrush through a spray deposition technique. A platinum loading of 1.8 mg·cm⁻² was applied to the anode.

For the cathode, the ink was prepared by sonicating a 40% Pt/C catalyst (Alfa Aesar, Ward Hill, MA, USA) with the same 33 wt.% Nafion® ionomer. A Pt loading of 0.5 mg·cm⁻² was applied to the cathode. The resulting electrodes were cold pressed onto a Nafion® 115 proton exchange membrane (PEM) to assemble the membrane electrode assembly (MEA). The MEA was tested using a 5 cm² single-cell hardware setup from Fuel Cell Technologies Inc. During testing, a 2 M methanol solution was supplied to the anode at a flow rate of 2 mL·min⁻¹. The cathode was continuously purged with fully humidified nitrogen at a flow rate of 100 mL·min⁻¹ under atmospheric pressure. Performance evaluation was conducted in steady-state mode at 90 °C. Linear sweep voltammetry (LSV) was performed at a scan rate of 5 mV·s⁻¹ across a potential range from 0.1 to 1 V, using a Metrohm Autolab potentiostat/galvanostat.

3. Results

The electrochemical behaviour of the 50% PtRu/C catalyst derived from the mixing of the Pt and Ru sulphite precursors or the impregnation of RuCl₃ over Pt sulphite was initially evaluated for the methanol oxidation reaction (MOR) using a glassy carbon (GC) disk as the working electrode in a half-cell configuration. The experiments were conducted in 0.5 M

sulfuric acid, with a methanol concentration of 2 M, and the linear sweep voltammetry (LSV) results are shown in Figure 2. The peak current density observed at 0.7 V was 9.4 mA cm⁻² for PtRu/C derived by the mixing of the sulphite precursors and 6.6 mA cm⁻² for PtRu/C derived by impregnation.

Figure 2. LSV curves in RDE for the 50 wt.% PtRu/C catalysts derived from the mixing of sulphite precursors or impregnation at 2 M methanol concentrations in 0.5 M H₂SO₄

The ethanol electroreforming (ER) cell was assembled using a Nafion 115 proton exchange membrane as the electrolyte. The cathode consisted of a commercial 40% Pt/C catalyst (0.5 mgPt cm⁻²) coated onto an SGL 39BB gas diffusion layer (GDL), while the anode employed the in-house-prepared 50% PtRu/C catalysts also supported on GDL. A 2 M methanol solution was supplied to the anode side, and nitrogen gas was introduced into the cathode compartment. Figure 3 presents linear sweep voltammetry (LSV) curves recorded at 90 °C. At 1 V cell potential, the performances for the two MEAs are similar, with the achievement of 1.78 and 1.73 A cm⁻².

Figure 3. LSV curves in 5 cm² ER cell for the PtRu/C//Nafion 115//Pt/C MEAs derived from the mixing of sulphite precursors or impregnation at 2 M methanol solutions and 90°C

4. Conclusions

Electrochemical reforming (ER) of alcohols presents a promising alternative to conventional water electrolysis for hydrogen production. One of its key advantages is the ability to achieve current densities exceeding 1 A cm⁻² at relatively low cell voltages (< 1 V), in contrast to a potential >1.8 V typically required for the oxygen evolution reaction (OER) in water electrolysis. In this work, the 50% Pt₁Ru₁/C anode catalysts, derived from the mixing of the Pt and Ru sulphite precursors or the impregnation of RuCl₃ over Pt sulphite, were synthesized. These catalysts, employed at the anode of two ER cells operated at 90 °C with a 2 M methanol feed at the anode, achieved current densities above 1.7 A cm⁻² at a cell voltage of 1 V.

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